

Mucopolysaccharidosis in Two Patients Within the Same Family - Surgical Treatment and Prospects of an Early Diagnosis

Marie E. Horstmann*, Adrian Gericke, Alexander K. Schuster, Norbert Pfeiffer, Joanna Wasielica-Poslednik

Department of Ophthalmology, University Medical Center of the Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz, Mainz, Germany

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***Corresponding author:** Marie E. Horstmann, Department of Ophthalmology, University Medical Center of the Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz, Langenbeckstr. 155131 Mainz, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Mucopolysaccharidoses (MPS) comprise rare metabolic lysosomal storage disorders affecting multiple organs. Timely diagnosis and effective treatment are crucial for extending lifespan and enhancing quality of life. We explore ocular findings and treatment in two closely related MPS patients, investigating their family tree involving identical twin parents.

Observations: Two female cousins born in 2000 and 2002, diagnosed with autosomal recessive MPS type I (Hurler-Scheie), presented with progressing corneal opacities. Hematopoietic stem cell transplantation was conducted in their first year of life. Visual impairment emerged at the age of 17 years for patient #1 and 10 for patient #2. Initial clinic examination revealed bilateral stromal opacity (Coupric grade III). Penetrating Keratoplasty (PK) was performed on both eyes for patient #1 at the age of 20 and 21 years and for patient #2 at the age of 10 and 13 years, respectively. Patient #2 experienced elevated Intraocular Pressure (IOP) several years after PK, leading to trabeculectomy at 20. PK improved visual acuity without corneal opacity recurrence at 2 and 10-year follow-up. However, patient #2 exhibited reduced visual acuity due to MPS related secondary open-angle glaucoma.

Conclusions and Importance: To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report on MPS I patients with identical twin parents. The heightened incidence of MPS in this family highlights the importance of comprehensive family history. Early systemic and ocular therapy proves beneficial for MPS patients with corneal opacities or glaucoma. Despite early stem cell transplantation, corneal opacity progressed in our two cases, impacting vision. Penetrating keratoplasties proved effective in improving visual acuity for both patients. Both patients required an IOP-lowering treatment.

Keywords: Mucopolysaccharidosis type 1; MPS; MPS-associated corneal opacity; Penetrating keratoplasty

Case Report (ISSN: 2832-5788)**INTRODUCTION**

Mucopolysaccharidoses (MPS) constitute a group of metabolic disorders caused by the absence or malfunction of specific lysosomal enzymes responsible for degradation of Glycosaminoglycans (GAG). Altered metabolites accumulate in intracellular vacuoles of various tissues and organs and can also be found in the urine [1]. In Germany, the estimated incidence of all MPS forms is 1:28,000, mainly inherited in an autosomal-recessive manner, except for MPS II (Hunter's disease), which follows X-linked recessive inheritance [2]. The autosomal-recessive inheritance pattern results in both parents of a phenotypically affected individual carrying one copy of the mutated gene, typically asymptomatic. So far, there are seven (formerly nine) recognized forms of MPS, with MPS III being the most prevalent and MPS IX the rarest. Most MPS manifestations encompass progressive skeletal deformities, short stature, coarsened facial features, and other organ abnormalities, exhibiting highly variable symptom expression [3]. Metabolite accumulation can affect the eyes, leading to pathological changes. In the cornea, these typically result in punctate or diffuse stromal opacities, varying in severity depending on the form of MPS and leading to visual impairment or even loss of vision.

Notably, in MPS I (Hurler, Hurler-Scheie, or Scheie types), corneal deposits are most pronounced, often present at birth, and result in stromal opacities caused by altered collagen fibril organization resulting from the accumulation of GAG [4]. Severity is graded according to the Couprie scale. The severity ranges from no visible opacity (grade 1) to an inability to evaluate the anterior chamber and fundus (grade 4) [5].

Metabolites may also accumulate at the posterior pole, causing pigmentary retinopathy and/or optic disc atrophy. The occurrence of elevated intraocular pressure and glaucoma may also be associated with MPS. From an ophthalmological perspective, various corneal or partial corneal transplantation options can be considered.

Systemic therapies include Hematopoietic Stem Cell Transplantation (HSCT) or Enzyme Replacement Therapies (ERT) for specific MPS types. HSCT involves transplanting healthy donor cells, with the secreted enzyme aiding in cross-correction [6]. ERT, delivered intravenously, supplies the deficient enzyme, breaking down accumulated GAG and mitigating organ damage. While clinical efficacy and safety of ERT are confirmed, limited improvements in the eyes, even with prolonged treatment, are attributed to the restricted penetration of recombinant enzymes into ocular tissues [7].

This report details the conservative and surgical ophthalmological interventions for two related MPS type I patients. Notably, the parents of these two girls are identical twins to the parents of the other girl.

METHODS

We present a case description and literature review on patients with MPS type I. All patients were evaluated at the Department of Ophthalmology of the University Medical Center of the Johannes-Gutenberg University Mainz. Written informed consent was obtained from both patients.

RESULTS

The patient # 1's parents were monozygotic twins of the parents of patient # 2 (Figure 1).

Case 1

A 17-year-old Caucasian girl underwent initial examination at our clinic in 2017 with progressing bilateral visual impairment. Her medical history included MPS type I (Hurler-Scheie), arterial hypertension,

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cardiomyopathy, sensorineural hearing loss, and multiple intracranial cavernomas, with a history of HSCT in her first year of life.

During the initial examination, her best Corrected Visual Acuity (CDVA) was 0.4/0.4 (log MAR). Refraction revealed +6,00 D sphere -3,50 D cylinder 8° axis on the right, and the left eye was not measurable. Both corneas exhibited diffuse MPS-associated stromal opacity (Couprie grade III) (Figure 2). The anterior chamber was deep and quiet bilaterally, with a round pupil, normal iris, and clear lens. Fundoscopy revealed regular optic discs and an unremarkable retina. Local therapy with prostaglandin analogs once daily was initiated six months prior for moderate ocular hypertension (24/21 mmHg), and Intraocular Pressure (IOP) was normal at presentation (18/19 mmHg).

Figure 1: Family tree of patient #1 and patient #2: Patient #1 and #2 are cousins whose parents both had monozygotic twins.

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Figure 2: Front section photos of patient #1: diffuse stromal opacity (Couprie grade **III**) of the cornea in mucopolysaccharidosis type **I** in diffuse lighting (upper left) and in slit lighting (upper right); clear graft with double-running diagonal cross-stitch suture according to Hoffmann after penetrating keratoplasty in diffuse lighting (lower left); clear graft without sutures and with a hard contact lens (lower right).

Figure 3: Front section photos of patient #2: diffuse stromal opacity of the cornea in mucopolysaccharidosis type **I** in diffuse lighting and optical coherence tomography of the central cornea presenting diffuse stromal opacity and central corneal thickness of 518 μm .

Over the subsequent three years, her CDVA declined to 0.5/0.5 (log MAR), prompting the decision for surgical intervention. Penetrating Keratoplasties (PKs) were performed on both eyes within a year. Postoperatively, topical therapy included dexamethasone, initially 6 times daily for 4 weeks, with a gradual reduction by 1 drop per month to 1 drop daily, along with antibiotic eyedrops (ofloxacin) for 1 week and artificial tears (Povidon). To detect, treat and prevent possible recurrence of herpes infection in corneal grafts and to support graft survival, we routinely perform polymerase-chain-reaction (PCR) in all excised corneas [8]. Due to the detection of herpes simplex virus 1 (HSV-1) in the excised cornea of this patient, antiviral therapy with topical ganciclovir 1.5 mg/1 g and systemic acyclovir 2 mg \times 400 mg was applied for 1 year. The patient experienced an increase in IOP on the left eye up to 30 mmHg, requiring additional pressure-lowering therapy with a combination of carbonic anhydrase inhibitor (dorzolamide) and a beta-blocker (timolol). One-year post-PK, the refraction was

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+6,00 D sphere -4,75 D cylinder 4° axis (on the right) and +1,25 D sphere -4,75 D cylinder 160° axis (on the left eye). Corneal sutures were removed and a rigid gas-permeable contact lens was fitted for astigmatism and sphere correction. At the two-year follow-up, the grafts were clear without any signs of rejection or recurrence of corneal clouding, CDVA (logMAR) was 0.2 (right eye) and 0.1 (left eye) with a contact lens. The IOP was 12 mmHg with pressure lowering eyedrops (timolol and dorzolamide twice daily) and a maintenance dose of 1 drop dexamethasone daily.

Case 2

A 10-year-old cousin of the first patient, with a positive family history of MPS type I, was diagnosed at the age of 3 months and underwent a HSCT at 10 months. At the age of 10 years, she presented with progressive visual deterioration. CDVA (logMAR) was 0.8 (right eye) and 0.7 (left eye). Refraction revealed +0,5 D sphere -1,25 D cylinder 137° axis on the left eye. Refraction on the right eye was not measurable by the NIDEK refractometer. We found MPS-associated diffuse stromal opacities (Couprie grade 3) in both eyes (Figure 3). The anterior chamber was deep, and the lens was clear. The retina was only poorly assessable due to the corneal opacities. PK was successfully performed on the right eye. The IOP was normal without IOP-lowering therapy (15 mmHg). Three years later, a PK was required for the left eye due to decreased visual acuity. Postoperatively, therapy mirrored that of her cousin, but without antiviral therapy. Corneal sutures were removed one-year post-PK.

At the next follow-up visit - six years after PK - the IOP in the left eye was 40 mmHg despite 4-fold therapy with a carbonic anhydrase inhibitor, a beta-blocker, alpha-2 agonist, and a prostaglandin analog. Optic nerve presented severe excavation (cup-to-disc-ratio 0.9). Therefore, probe trabeculotomy in combination with mitomycin C (MMC) was successfully performed on the left eye. At the follow-up of one-year post-trabeculotomy (ten years post-PK on the right and 8 years post PK on the left eye) visual acuity with contact lens was 0.3 and 0.8 (log MAR), with normal IOP values of 15 and 10 mmHg without topical therapy. The corneal grafts were clear and without signs of recurrence of opacities. The poor visual acuity in the left eye (most likely resulting from the damage to the optic nerve) led to decompensated esophoria of the left eye, whereupon strabismus surgery was performed.

Eight years after removal of the corneal sutures on the right and five years after removal on the left eye, visual acuity was 0.4/1.0 (right/left logMAR). The refraction of the fitted lenses was -4,25 D sphere -4,25 D cylinder 87° axis (on the right) and -6,5 D sphere -9,0 D cylinder 13° axis (on the left eye).

DISCUSSION

We report on two female patients suffering from ophthalmological and extraocular pathologies associated with mucopolysaccharidosis. Both individuals, cousins, share the rare autosomal recessive inherited metabolic disorder MPS type I (Hurler-Scheie). The genetic burden within this family stems from the fact that the parents of these two girls are monozygotic twins to the parents of the other girl, resulting in an increased likelihood of both sets of parents being heterozygous carriers of the genetic disorder. Consequently, the statistical probability of their offspring being affected by MPS type I was 25%. Both patients exhibited stromal opacities of the cornea, which are the most common ocular disorders affecting MPS patients. Both girls underwent HSCT in the first year of life. However, this therapy has only a minimal effect on the development of corneal opacities [9].

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Van den Broek et al. report in a prospective study including 24 patients with MPS-1 that despite stem cell transplantation, corneal opacities increased rapidly beyond 3 years. Furthermore, IOP and CDVA worsened significantly over time [10]. Since corneal opacities and CDVA worsened also in both of our patients, eventually, PK was performed in both cases. In patient #1, CDVA improved from 0.5/0.5 (logMAR right/left) to 0.2 and 0.1 (logMAR right/left) respectively. Patient #2 also benefited from the PK and presented change of the visual acuity from 0.8 and 0.7 (logMAR right/left) to 0.4 and 1.0 (logMAR right/left), whereas CDVA in the left eye has not increased most likely due to glaucomatous optic nerve damage. Both patients showed either an ocular hypertension or glaucoma besides the corneal opacities: In patient #1, three years before the first PK, an increase in IOP was observed in both eyes, so that local therapy with prostaglandin analogs was initiated. On the left eye, one year postoperatively, the IOP increased up to 30 mmHg. Therefore, topical steroids were paused, and topical dorzolamide and timolol were supplemented in both eyes. This could successfully lower and control the IOP. We put the late increase in IOP on the back of secondary open-angle glaucoma rather than the effect of steroids. In patient #2, six years after PK, an increase in IOP and a decrease of the optic nerve fiber layer were observed in the left eye, so that secondary open-angle glaucoma was diagnosed, and local therapy was initiated. The rise of IOP in patients with MPS is assumed to result from an accumulation of GAG in the trabecular meshwork, leading to impaired outflow of aqueous humor. Therefore, patients with MPS require regular assessment for possible glaucoma, including during childhood [7]. Previous studies estimated the prevalence of glaucoma in MPS to be between 2.1 and 21.5%, whereby the number of undiagnosed cases could be even higher because glaucoma diagnosis can be considerably more difficult in patients with MPS. Wasilica-Poslednik et al. investigated the influence of corneal opacity on IOP assessment in patients with lysosomal storage diseases (including MPS) and found that the prevalence of glaucoma could not be specified in their cohort as the optic discs could not be assessed in many cases [11]. Furthermore, a study showed relevant differences in IOP resulting from MPS-related corneal clouding, depending on the technique and device of tonometry: Measurements assessed with an Ocular Response Analyzer (ORA) seemed to be less affected by corneal rigidity and therefore more precise than those using applanation or rebound tonometry (for example, the iCare-tonometer) [12].

In the case of our patient #2, the IOP could not be sufficiently regulated by local antiglaucomatous treatment. It increased up to 40 mmHg, whereupon we decided to perform a probe trabeculotomy in combination with MMC due to the macroscopic open anterior chamber angle and patient's young age. The improved outflow of the aqueous humor led to normal IOP-values. Up-to-date, there is no clear recommendation for a surgical treatment pattern in MPS patients.

Mucopolysaccharidoses are genetic, congenital metabolic disorders. Due to the possibly non-specific initial symptoms of MPS patients, the suspicion of MPS is often not obvious in young patients. Ophthalmologists may play a decisive role here. They are sometimes the first to suspect a metabolic disease due to the possible ocular manifestations. Nevertheless, diagnosis is often delayed and represents a major problem affecting all MPS types to a greater or lesser extent. The average delay in diagnosis from the time of onset of symptoms is 2.9 years, depending on the MPS type [13]. Since an early diagnosis and treatment can have a positive effect on the course of the disease, abnormal clinical findings should be presented to a specialized center for further clarification. In case of evidence for a lysosomal storage disease, the diagnosis can be confirmed, and appropriate therapy can be

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initiated at an early stage. HSCT or ERT can be effective systemic therapeutic options, depending on the patient's age and symptoms. In HSCT, the enzyme secreted by the transplanted donor cells is taken up by the recipient's body, leading to a degradation of the accumulated GAG. HSCT has proven positive impact on disease manifestations and quality of life [6]. A positive effect on the excretion of accumulated GAG and on organomegaly has also been proven for ERT, but the effect on ocular structures is debated in several studies. Especially if therapy is initiated relatively late, a clearing of the cornea is unusual, most likely due to the reduced penetrance of ocular tissue and impermeability of the blood-brain barrier [14-16]. Nevertheless, an early diagnosis improves not only the systemic prognosis but is also essential for the early treatment of ocular complications such as glaucoma, corneal opacity, and for the prophylaxis of amblyopia [4]. Up to now, penetrating- or Deep Lamellar Keratoplasty (DALK) are the surgical treatment options for severe MPS-associated corneal opacification. We recommend performing keratoplasty as soon as the anterior chamber or fundus cannot be assessed due to the opacity. Studies showed a successful corneal transplantation in MPS patients with a clear graft in 94% of cases over a period of 70 months after PK. In case of our patient #2 the graft remained clear for at least 10 years (until the end of follow-up). Rejection episodes with 23% of grafts in MPS patients were comparable to the general 5-year rejection rate after PK in high-risk situations (such as deep vascularization of the cornea in ≥ 2 quadrants, a transplant close to the limbus, severe rheumatoid arthritis and other factors) [17]. We do not experience such a high rate of immune rejections in our patients' cohort. Reappearance of corneal opaqueness of the transplanted graft can happen as soon as the first year after transplant, since GAG deposits re-accumulate in donor keratocytes [14]. Some authors suggest that MPS forms with dermatan sulfate accumulation (MPS VI, MPS VII) present a better outcome after PK than forms with keratan sulfate accumulation (MPS IV) [18]. Nevertheless, international studies were able to show a successful visual outcome in 63% of cases after PK in MPS patients with a follow-up of 70 months and a clear graft at last follow-up was recorded in 94% [19]. In some cases, a Deep Anterior Lamellar Keratoplasty (DALK) can be an alternative surgical treatment. Besides the classic advantages of partial transplantation, such as better integrity in the event of trauma or lack of endothelial rejection, preserving the patient's own endothelium is discussed to offer better resistance not only to traumas but also to re-accumulation of GAG deposits in the cornea. In this case, up to the day of publication at the follow-up of 2 and 10 years, the patients' corneal grafts remained clear and did not show any reappearance of corneal opaqueness. The sutures could be removed, and patients cope very well in everyday life with fitted hard contact lenses to compensate for astigmatism.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, our cases highlight the importance of comprehensive family history, emphasizing the heightened incidence of MPS within consanguineous families. Early systemic and ocular therapy proves beneficial for MPS patients with corneal opacities or glaucoma. Ophthalmologists, often the first to suspect lysosomal storage diseases in mild MPS cases, play a pivotal role in achieving early diagnoses. Corneal transplantation emerges as an effective treatment option, significantly improving visual acuity in the majority of cases. Continuous vigilance for glaucoma remains imperative in this patient group.

Case Report (ISSN: 2832-5788)**PATIENT CONSENT**

Consent to publish this case report has been obtained from the patient(s) in writing.

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